

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D7.2 1st dissemination & communication report

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Table 1: Channels of Communication and Dissemination and their relative KPIs and Targeted Values

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Effective dissemination and communication are important to assure that the TraceMyFish project results reach the appropriate stakeholders both during and at the end of the project duration. Work Package 7 is specially devoted to the dissemination and communication activities, as well as tackling responsible research and innovation (RRI) aspects of the project.

This communications and dissemination report (D7.2) gives a description of the main communications and dissemination activities which the TraceMyFish consortium during the first project year, and gives an updated plan of the upcoming activities that will be incorporated during the second (and last) project year. Furthermore, the report summarizes the dissemination and communication progress based on the key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in the Communications and dissemination plan (D7.1) to monitor the progress within Work package 7.

The monitoring of the KPIs were used to assess the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activities, which will be summarized and reported on an annual basis throughout the project duration. The mid-project evaluation (M12) will, furthermore, be used to identify stakeholder groups that might require further attention in the dissemination activities, and these groups will thus be targeted specifically in the second year of the project.

Deliverable 7.2 will be followed up with the second annual reporting on the communications and dissemination activities (deliverable 7.3, due in M24), as well as by the submission of annual reports on human capacity building (HCB) activities facilitated by the TraceMyFish project (deliverables 7.4-7.5 in M12 and M24, respectively).

1 INTRODUCTION

Effective dissemination and communication are important to assure that the TraceMyFish project results reach the appropriate stakeholders both during and at the end of the project duration. Work Package 7 is specially devoted to the dissemination and communication activities, as well as tackling responsible research and innovation (RRI) aspects of the project.

The following sections describe the original dissemination and communication plan (Task 7.1) and its continuous updates during the project duration (Task 7.3), including descriptions of planned and executed engagement with stakeholders (Task 7.2), and mobility and human capacity building (HCB) activities within the project (Task 7.4).

An overview of the communication and dissemination activities were included in the accepted proposal, and they are summarized in the following section 2. Updates on planned and finished activities will then be provided in section 3 of this report.

2 WORK PACKAGE DESCRIPTION ACCORDING TO PROPOSAL

Objectives:

A well-structured *Communication and Dissemination plan* is crucial to make sure that the outputs of TraceMyFish contribute to the expected impacts on economical, societal (including ethical, legal and social aspects, ELSA), and effective knowledge generation and transfer to a wide audience of stakeholders.

The WP is divided into the following tasks:

- T7.1 Dissemination and communication plan (M1-M3)
- T7.2 Stakeholder engagement and open dialogue activities (M4-M24)
- T7.3 Dissemination and communication activities (M1-M24)
- T7.4 Mobility, skills, and capacity building for Blue Bioeconomy professionals (M12-M24)

Description:

The objective of WP7 is to effectively summarize all knowledge generation obtained in the TraceMyFish project and transfer it to the appropriate audience in an effective way according to the TraceMyFish Communication and Dissemination plan presented here.

The planned communication and dissemination of the TraceMyFish outputs and results. A wide range of communication and dissemination channels are included in the plan as set up in Task 7.1. The plan will be put into action and updated continuously throughout the project as described in Task 7.2-4.

The list of deliverables in WP7 show an overview of the main communication and dissemination activities that are planned in the TraceMyFish project. A detailed communications and dissemination plan will be set up and delivered in M3 (Task 7.1), which will be followed through and executed in Tasks 7.2-7.4, as seen in the task descriptions.

All TraceMyFish partners contribute to the Work Package since this ensures active knowledge generation and transfer to both academia and industry, as well as their consumers and collaborators.

2.1 TASK 7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN (M1-M3)

The objective of Task 7.1 is to set up a dissemination and communication plan for the project, including the following activities:

- TraceMyFish official homepage and social media pages
- active communication of TraceMyFish results and outputs through participants' homepages and social media
- scientific peer-reviewed articles in high impact, open access journals
- project workshops, courses, and conferences
- stakeholder engagement at workshops, conferences, and meetings (Task 7.2)
- mobility and capacity building activities of students and BlueBioeconomy professionals (Task 7.4).
- MSc. and Ph.D. student theses and defenses, and associated peer-reviewed scientific publications
- Videos, brochures, popular news etc. for consumers and general public.

A detailed dissemination and communication plan will be set up in the first 3 months of the project (Deliverable 7.1). The plan will then be revised and updated and reported on continuously throughout the project duration in Tasks 7.2-7.4 as needed.

2.2 TASK 7.2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND OPEN DIALOGUE (M4-M24)

Stakeholder engagement and open dialogue activities in the TraceMyFish project include holding two workshops for the project participants as well as other relevant industrial, research, research funding bodies, policy making and consumer stakeholders on the project progress and outcomes. Two events are planned, one at the middle (M12) and one at the end of the project (M24).

2.3 TASK 7.3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES (M1-M24)

The dissemination and communication activities plan set up in Task 7.1 will be updated continuously throughout the project duration and set into action within Task 7.3.

The progress on the project dissemination and communication will be summarized in two reports at M12 and M24, respectively (Deliverable 7.2).

2.4 TASK 7.4 MOBILITY, SKILLS, AND CAPACITY BUILDING (M13-M24).

A structured plan for mobility and capacity building activities of students and professionals will be established to ensure interdisciplinary collaboration and exchange of knowledge and skills among the partners. Mobility of young researchers as well as joint supervision of master diploma thesis and internships will be of high priority. VIDEOM is a leading company in spectral imaging technology for applications in food. They will provide training action and provide a handheld instrument to all involved partners. VIDEOM will also provide a demonstration of the VideometerLite instrument for stakeholders [at the Food Technology conference in 2022](#).

2.5 LIST OF ASSOCIATED MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES:

M7.1 Targets and venues collected (M2)

M7.2 HCB activities designed (M15)

D7.1 Dissemination and communication plan (M3)

D7.2 1st dissemination and communication report (M12)

D7.3 2nd dissemination and communication report (M24)

D7.4 1st HCB activities report (M12)

D7.5 2nd HCB activities report (M24)

3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

TraceMyFish, from its inception stage, has foreseen and dedicated a work package (WP7) for the planning and execution of broad communication and dissemination activities so as to maximize the outreach and impact of the project. In particular, Task 7.1 had the specific target of formulating a concrete dissemination and communication strategy. According to the defined strategy, the main goals of the TraceMyFish dissemination and communication activities cover three key strategic directions: (a) Raising public awareness and ensuring maximum visibility of the project key facts, outputs and findings amongst the public; (b) Supporting the transfer of project results and engagement from key stakeholders in academia and industry (c) Enhancing the commercial potential of the results and users’ reception. Taking into account the innovativeness of the proposed solution and, thus, its probable need to mature beyond the scope of the project, a hierarchical model emphasizing the initial steps of user engagement, such as AIDA (Rawal, 2013) and its variations, is particularly suitable for TraceMyFish. The model identifies four hierarchical, sequential stages that culminate to stakeholder engagement:

1. **Awareness:** refers to the creation and promotion of the TraceMyFish identity that will be able to establish itself as a standard imagery evocating the project’s concept and scope;
2. **Interest:** refers to the means used to communicate and highlight the added value of the TraceMyFish solutions in a way that raises the interest of targeted audiences;
3. **Desire:** deals with the modalities through which audiences will be motivated to test the TraceMyFish solutions and actively participate in its ecosystem;
4. **Action:** incorporates the strategic steps for transforming knowledge, interest, and motivation into active engagement, either as part of a growing TraceMyFish community or as part of a client base.

As such the project’s approach included as early on as M6 the present D7.1 deliverable that compiles a concrete communication and dissemination plan spanning across all four AIDA axes. The plan was construed in order to effectively spread the TraceMyFish message to the relevant communities. For each measure included in the plan specific KPIs and targets have been identified (Table 1).

Table 2: Channels of Communication and Dissemination and their relative KPIs and Targeted Values

Channel #	Channel Name	KPI Code	KPI Description	Targeted Value (Year 1)	Targeted Value (Year 2) ¹
1	TraceMyFish website	KPI1.1	Visits	≥1,000	≥2,000
		KPI1.2	Downloads	50	≥250
		KPI1.3	Newsletter subscribers	≥100	≥200
2	TraceMyFish social media	KPI2.1	Social media posts (Tweets, LinkedIn, Facebook)	50	≥100
		KPI2.2	Twitter Followers	100	≥300
		KPI2.3	LinkedIn Page Members	100	≥200
		KPI2.4	Facebook Page Followers	100	≥200
3		KPI3.1	Journal Publications	1	≥4

¹ Accumulated value.

	Scientific publications	KPI3.2	Conference Proceedings	2	≥6
4	Press relations	KPI4.1	Newspaper/Magazine Articles	1	≥4
		KPI4.2	Interviews and Presentations	1	≥2
5	Event participation	KPI5.1	Scientific Conferences/Workshops	4	>12
		KPI5.2	Industry Events	1	>4

For the fruition and realization of this strategy the following components have been selected and already activated as will be explained in the following chapters.

- a. **Visual identity:** It entails the project’s logo, imagery, typography, colours, and creative design. These will be consistently used in communication materials and project outcomes. Templates and guidelines for building different content types have already been produced and will be used throughout its duration.
- b. **Project website:** The consortium has already set the project’s website and will maintain it for at least two years after the project’s completion. The website includes a public area through which public information will be disseminated, as well as a private area for the distribution of information restricted to the consortium.
- c. **Social media:** the project will also engage in the effective usage of social media for disseminating information to the general public (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn) and the research community (e.g., ResearchGate). We will consider using YouTube for distributing video material, such as tutorials and infomercials. All social media accounts have been created.
- d. **Communication and dissemination materials:** For this channel, the partners distinctly divide the outcomes into two distinct channels, one for more specialized scientific audiences and one addressed to more general audiences in order to raise awareness. Therefore, the former includes scientific publications, posters, and articles mainly addressed to scientific experts and professionals. Exemplary high-impact journals that will be targeted are: Food Chemistry, LWT-Food Science and Technology, Journal of Food Engineering, Food Research International, MDPI-Foods, Scientific reports etc. Regarding software assets and source code, they will be made available through public repositories like GitHub. General interest material includes leaflets, brochures, fact sheets and multimedia assets, to be distributed either online or physically.
- e. **Events and networks:** TraceMyFish outcomes will be presented to academic and non-academic audiences, including conferences and relevant workshops. Prospective academic conferences which could be targeted for research presentations include:
 1. Anuga FoodTech
 2. Nordic FoodTech
 3. IASIM
 4. EFFoST
 5. WEFTA
 6. AquaNor

Furthermore, industry partners will demonstrate the project results at industrial, international large expositions and trade fairs. A workshop or a topical session integrated within suitable conferences will be held at appropriate stages in the work (concepts, results progress, and final dissemination). Finally, each partner, in collaboration with local communities, will set up one demonstration unit to spread the

message and create awareness on food safety and fish chain monitoring. Project flyers, technical brochures and best practice abstracts will be prepared and made available to disseminate the project outputs.

- f. **Press relations:** Regarding media targeted to a broader audience, TraceMyFish will design and prepare articles, talks, presentations, and demonstrations to be used in mainstream channels like newspapers, magazines, radio and TV.
- g. **Impact monitoring:** In order to measure and evaluate the impact of the TraceMyFish communication and dissemination strategy, a set of quantifiable success indicators are established (Table 1), setting the basis for assessing the fulfilment of the objectives. For online channels, we will use relevant analytics tools where available (e.g., Google Analytics, Twitter Analytics).

4 ONLINE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The updates on the tasks in WP7 will be discussed in unison in this report due to their close relations and to avoid repetitions. All activities are marked according to the dates that they are finished.

4.1 VISUAL IDENTITY OF TRACEMYFISH

Logos and templates for all deliverables and presentations are available to project partners on the google docs workspace shared with the project participants. These include the following:

[Template for deliverables](#)

[Template for PPT presentations](#)

Logos for each participant is available on page 3 of this deliverable.

Moreover, the project logo is presented below.

Figure 1: TraceMyFish Project Logo

4.2 TRACEMYFISH OFFICIAL HOMEPAGE

4.2.1 Objective

Active communication of TraceMyFish results and outputs through participants' homepages and newsletter.

4.2.2 Description

An official homepage of the project and associated social media pages have been launched to give the project an official face towards stakeholders, including the funding bodies, industry, academia, and consumers. Links to these pages are provided here:

Homepage: tracemyfish.hi.is (final polishing of connections, will be launched before May 15th).

The target KPI include obtaining more than 1000 visits to the homepage within the first project year, and more than 2000 visits at the end of year 2 (KPI 1.1).

The project also aims at sending out project updates in a Newsletter, reaching an audience of >100 stakeholders by the first project year, and >200 at the end of the project duration.

Access to open access articles, newsletters, and other communication and dissemination material will be provided on the TraceMyFish homepage. The consortium aims at achieving at least 50 downloads of the project material by year 1, and over 250 downloads by year 2.

4.2.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The official TraceMyFish project homepage was launched during spring 2022. The homepage summarizes the main project objectives, presents the project partners and scientists, information on the project funding from the BlueBio Cofund, news and events and links to social media platforms. More detailed information on the pilot cases, and information on project progress related and scientific publications are added as they are published.

The project progress reports, including deliverable reports from TraceMyFish can also be seen on the following Zenodo page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/tracemyfish/?page=1&size=20>

4.3 SOCIAL MEDIA PRESENCE

4.3.1 Objective

Active communication of TraceMyFish results and outputs through the project social media channels.

4.3.2 Description

The following social media channels have been established for the TraceMyFish project on Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook:

Twitter page: TraceMyFish @Trace_My_Fish

LinkedIn: TraceMyFish <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12641322/>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/TraceMyFish>

The project activities will be communicated and active means will be taken to promote the project activities and the project participants' activities in related projects, conferences, publications and interactions with stakeholders.

The KPIs that will be monitored throughout the project include the number of tweets and posts on the social media platforms, number of followers and likes. The target values are given in Table 1 on page 13.

4.3.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The TraceMyFish social media platforms were set up during the spring of 2022, including a Twitter page, a LinkedIn page, and a Facebook page. Since the launch a total of 48 posts have been made to the social media platforms. The aim was set to 50 posts during the first year (KPI 2.1) and to over a hundred posts at the end of the project duration. More posts will be shared on the social media platforms as more detailed publications and dissemination and communication activities will be produced within the project. The aims of KPI 2.2 will thus likely be reached within the project duration.

The total number of followers on Twitter are currently at 91, which is close to the goal number of Twitter followers (KPI 2.2) of 100 for the first year. Likewise, the LinkedIn followers currently add up to 89, which also measures close to the goal number of 100 LinkedIn followers (KPI 2.3). Further promotion of the sites will continue, so that the total follower goals of over 300 Twitter followers, and 200 LinkedIn followers within the project duration may be achieved. Promotions of the Facebook site has gone slower, and the Facebook project fan base not close to the target number of followers (KPI 2.4 of 100 followers). However, the different social media platforms include different stakeholder compositions, and is also varying between countries. Facebook

is regarded as a B2C social media platform, while Twitter and LinkedIn are more directed towards scientists and industrial professionals. All three social media platforms may thus be useful for overall project dissemination and communication purposes at the end of the project.

4.4 PRESS RELATIONS

4.4.1 Objective

To communicate the TraceMyFish results and outcomes to a wide audience through press relations

4.4.2 Description

The TraceMyFish project has already gained some attention from the press and the objective of the consortium is to withhold active communications to various press relations to obtain active media presence of the project.

The KPIs monitored for this include the number of newspaper and magazine articles (KPI 4.1) and number of interviews and presentations (KPI 4.2)

4.4.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The TraceMyFish consortium has taken part in the following press and news relations:

1. **Interview of Dr. Panagiotis Zervas, SCiO (Coordinator of the project) about the aim of the project at powergame.gr a Greek information portal: <https://tinyurl.com/2p92cb6b>**
2. **Interview of Dr. Pythagoras Karampiperis (CEO of SCiO) about the aim of the project to EPT3 Greek national TV channel**
3. Videometer has agreed to an article on the Danish magazine PlusProces, which will focus on the use of the VideometerLite in the TraceMyFish project. This article is expected to be published in spring 2023.

With increased data gathering in the early months of 2023 the opportunity to take part in press releases and writing of newspaper articles will increase. The KPI 4.1 (>2 interviews) and KPI4.2 (>4 news articles) are thus likely to be achieved within the project duration.

5 OFFLINE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

5.1 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

5.1.1 Objective

The project results are expected to be published in several scientific peer-reviewed manuscripts in high-impact, open access journals. These publications are expected to include collaborative efforts between the TraceMyFish partners, and include MSc and PhD student research work, facilitating HCB within the project.

5.1.2 Descriptions

Below is a list of planned activities in this category:

- Scientific articles on the application of VideometerLite/VideometerLab in the studied pilot value chains.
 - Norway: Atlantic salmon value chain
 - Iceland: Atlantic whitefish value chain
 - Greece: Mediterranean seabream/seabass
- Scientific articles on the design/performance of the TraceMyFish iFMS

More opportunities for scientific publications may arise during the project duration. The number of scientific publications coming from the project may thus be reassessed in the midterm (M12) and final reports (M24).

5.1.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The aim was set to achieve the publication of at least one scientific publication by the end of year 1. Due to delays in performing trials within the pilot value chains will this publication also be delayed into the second project year. However, data acquisition within each value chain has started and the data are currently being assessed. The overall objectives of reaching the set KPI 5.1 of at least 4, are likely to be achieved within the project duration.

5.2 EVENTS PARTICIPATION

5.2.1 Objective

TraceMyFish participation and planning of workshops, courses and conferences are expected to increase the visibility of the project and its results. The list of potential activities will be updated continuously for the project meeting. These also include networking events on behalf of the BlueBio Cofund Secretariat.

5.2.2 Description

The following meetings, workshops, courses, and conference participations have been planned and/or have already taken place:

BlueBio Cofund joint kick-off meeting March 10th, 2022. TraceMyFish presentation.

BlueBio Cofund Human Capacity Building event, April 6th, 2022. TraceMyFish representation and participation.

Webinars by Videometer

Videometer participation at **ANUGA FoodTEch in Cologne** (T8.1 and T7.3) in 2022

Similar activities will continue to take place throughout the project duration.

5.2.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The following events participation have taken place in association with the TraceMyFish project during the first project year:

BlueBio Cofund events:

BlueBio Cofund joint kick-off meeting March 10th, 2022. TraceMyFish presentation.

BlueBio Cofund Human Capacity Building event, April 6th, 2022. TraceMyFish representation and participation.

Webinars by Videometer

BlueBio Cofund Commercialization support e-coffee meeting, October 28th, 2022. TraceMyFish project pitch presentation.

Scientific conferences and workshops participation (KPI 5.1 of 4 within first year, >12 for total project duration)

The project partners participated in the following scientific conferences, workshops, and industrial events where the TraceMyFish project was presented during the first project year:

Scientific conferences and workshops:

International scientists' night, October 1st, 2022 – poster presentations from AUA in Greece

The Icelandic food and nutrition society's general assembly, October 20th, 2022. – Oral presentation of TraceMyFish by Uol.

Sustainable Healthy Diets general assembly meeting, November 1st, 2022. – Oral presentation of TraceMyFish by Uol.

Industrial events (KPI 5.2 of 1 event participation in year 1, 4 within the project duration)

Videometer participation at **ANUGA FoodTEch in Cologne, Germany** (T8.1 and T7.3)

Videometer participation at **IASIM, Conference on spectral imaging** in Esbjerg, Denmark, July 3rd-6th, 2022 (T7.3 and T8.1) in 2022.

For the second year of the project several events participations are planned, including presentations of scientific data on the Whitefish and Salmon value chains at the EFFoST and WEFTA conferences.

Iceland is also the governing nation in the Nordic Arbejdsgruppe for fiskerisamarbejdet (AG-Fisk), which is a Nordic initiative funded by NordForsk, in the year 2023. The AG-Fisk consortium will therefore host several conferences and workshops in Iceland and surrounding Nordic countries, which will allow direct contact of the TraceMyFish partners to industrial stakeholders.

5.3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AT WORKSHOPS, CONFERENCES, AND MEETINGS

5.3.1 Objective

This activity is connected to Task 7.2 and WP2. The objective is to set up a combination of workshops and/or focus group interviews of stakeholders representing the three value chains with the aim of identifying gaps between stakeholders' needs for tracing hazards with non-destructive measures along the value chains and the current practice, and to give input into hazard identification within each value chain, as well as gain quality and safety data from each value chain. Secondly, conference and meeting activities are planned with the aim of the TraceMyFish results can reach a wide range of stakeholders' attention.

5.3.2 Description

The following stakeholder engagement activities have taken place:

- Stakeholders' meetings in Iceland performed in March 2022 with BRIM and Lýsi. Summary of results in meeting minutes from Jørgen Lerfall, Anita Alessia del Genio and María Guðjónsdóttir.
- VideometerLite set-up and training in Iceland finished in March 2022. Further feedback in relation to T3.2 in coming month.
- BRIM has agreed to allowing us to test the technique in their production. Follow-up planning meetings with BRIM before Easter, 2022.
- Meeting with ÚR on freezing processes of red fish April 4th, 2022. ÚR interested in adding quality check with VideometerLite and the VideometerLab during their onboard freezing processes. Activities planned in unison with Icelandic domestically funded research project "Bætt nýting vinnsluferla við sjófrystingu karfa – Matvælasjóður / Improved processes of onboard freezing of redfish").

Below is a list of planned activities in this category:

- Stakeholder meetings in Greece and Norway under preparation.

Further stakeholder engagement activities will be updated during the project duration.

5.3.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The following stakeholder meetings have been added since Deliverable 7.1 was handed in:

Stakeholder meetings with BRIM in Iceland on September 21st and October 12th, 2022, for planning of whitefish value chain activities.

Stakeholder meetings with Vísir hf, followed up by e-mail correspondence in October 2022 on Anisakis nematodes detection trials and planning of PhD student Andrea Rakeł Sigurðardóttir doctoral project.

Stakeholder activities and interactions with industry will continue during the second project year. To limit travel cost the consortium meetings will when applicable be planned in association with the timing of relevant conferences or workshops where the project can be presented, e.g., at WEFTA in Copenhagen 2023, and the beforementioned AG-Fisk activities in Iceland/Nordic countries in 2023.

6 HUMAN CAPACITY BUILDING (HCB) ACTIVITIES

6.1 FELLOWSHIPS TO POST-DOCS

6.1.1 Objective

The TraceMyFish consortium plans to provide the following fellowships to post-docs, PhD, and MSc. Students.

6.1.2 Description

Providing fellowship to post-docs, PhD and MSc students lays the basis for the human capacity building activities within the TraceMyFish consortium. Postgraduate students and post-docs will be invited to join short or medium term mobilities activities, as well as workshops, seminars and other in-person and online activities as described in sections 6.2-6.4.

KPIs associated with this task, is the number of fellowships provided, and their funding amounts.

6.1.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

At the end of year 2 the project involves the participation of at least two post-docs from AUA, one PhD student and a post-doc from NTNU, and one PhD student from the University of Iceland. Several MSc students and B.Sc. students doing short-term project will also be associated with the TraceMyFish project.

To ensure excellent human capacity building for these young researchers, they are partially or fully supervised by multiple TraceMyFish project participants. Short- or medium-term mobility within the different partners is encouraged, as summarized in section 6.2.

6.2 SHORT-MEDIUM TERM MOBILITY WITHIN THE PARTNERSHIP

6.2.1 Objective

Facilitate human capacity building through active communications between partners, experience exchange and communication of results both between TraceMyFish partners and to other stakeholders.

6.2.2 Description

The consortium encourages both short- and medium-term mobility of staff, especially younger researchers, and students to engage in mobility activities within the partnership. This includes visits to the partnering institutions, contributions to joint tasks and activities, and participation in joint webinars, seminars, workshops provided by the project partners.

Discussions on HCB activities within the TraceMyFish project as well as expanded activities have already started by project partner participation in the BlueBio Cofund joint events, such as the BlueBio HCB e-coffee meeting on April 6th, 2022.

KPIs associated with this are number and length of exchange activities between partners.

6.2.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

The following exchange activities and their durations have already been planned within the consortium:

- PhD student at UoI, Iceland will visit Videometer in Denmark in 2023. Estimated duration of the exchange is 2-3 weeks. The PhD student is supervised by partners from UoI, Matís and Videometer.
- PhD student at NTNU, Norway will visit UoI and Matís in Iceland in January 2023 to take part in the planned whitefish value chain activities during the spring. Estimated duration of the exchange is 1 month.

More activities are likely to develop during the second year of the project.

6.3 ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING COURSES AND/OR WEBINARS

6.3.1 Objective

Training courses and webinars will be developed and organized to showcase the TraceMyFish techniques to a wide audience.

6.3.2 Description

The TraceMyFish partners will develop and organize several training courses and/or webinars. These include for example the webinars provided by Videometer, which are available for both project participants as well as other interested parties, such as the following event:

- Free Webinar on March 31st, 2022, by Videometer, for both project participants and other interested stakeholders. <https://videometer.com /videometer-webinar-series-2022/>

Several training opportunities for industry, academia and consumers will be developed.

The KPIs involved with this part include the number of training courses provided within the consortium and number of participants.

6.3.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

Videometer have been effective in developing and providing a series of training webinars available both to specialists within and outside the TraceMyFish community. A summary of the available webinars for 2022 can be seen by following the link <https://videometer.com /videometer-webinar-series-2022/>

The webinars that have been held so far within the first year of the project are 5 and have attracted a wide audience of specialists.

Free Videometer webinar – March 31st, 2022

Spectral image acquisition and basic analysis – September 22nd, 2022

Machine learning or Spectral images – October 6th, 2022

Applications of spectral imaging for FoodAg integrity – October 20th, 2022

In depth nCDA, nMahalanobis, MNF/PCA – October 27th, 2022.

The following webinars are then further scheduled within the series:

Segmentation building – November 3rd, 2022

Session Recipe building – November 17th, 2022

Multispectral Fluorescence imaging with filter changer – December 1st, 2022

Introduction to CDT – December 15th, 2022.

More webinars will be added during the second project year.

6.4 ORGANIZATION OF UNIVERSITY COURSES

6.4.1 Objective

To effectively introduce the Videometer techniques to university students both by lectures and practical laboratory exercises.

6.4.2 Description

The TraceMyFish results and development of the Videometer techniques will be introduced in several university courses arranged by the participating universities (UoI, NTNU, AUA) at both undergraduate and graduate level.

6.4.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

During the first project year the Videometer techniques have already been introduced and incorporated into the following university courses:

University of Iceland – Faculty of Food Science and Nutrition MAT305G Food physics (lectures + laboratory exercise)

NTNU – Aquatic Food Production (AQFood) Joint MSc. Program – Aquatic food processing and technology (lecture)

The techniques are planned to be covered in the same courses for next year again. Furthermore, University of Iceland is currently planning and developing an edX course on the research developments and innovations in the marine sector, which will be available in the Fall semester 2023 as a part of the AQFood program mentioned earlier.

6.5 JOINT SUPERVISION OF MSC AND PHD STUDENTS

6.5.1 Objective

The TraceMyFish partners aim towards hosting joint MSc and PhD projects, and/or joint supervision of students.

6.5.2 Description

The TraceMyFish consortium will provide opportunities for MSc. and Ph.D. project that are either providing joint degrees or joint supervision between institutes. This also facilitates mobility opportunities for young researchers as described in section 6.2.

The KPIs associated with joint supervision of MSc and PhD students include the number of theses and defences, and associated peer-reviewed scientific publications and oral/poster student presentations at conferences and meetings.

6.5.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

As mentioned under section 6.2 the TraceMyFish project provides several student project opportunities, where they have joint supervision by the TraceMyFish partners. These include:

- **Andrea Rakel Sigurðardóttir, UoI**, whose PhD committee is composed by **María Guðjónsdóttir (UoI/Matís)**, **Hafsteinn Einarsson (UoI, Faculty of computer science)**, **Hildur Inga Sveinsdóttir (Matís/UoI)**, and **Nette Schultz (Videometer)**.
- **Sophie Kendler, NTNU**. Supervised by **Jørgen Lerfall** and **Anita Nordeng Jakobsen**. Planned HCB exchange with UoI and Matís in January 2023.

6.6 OTHER MEANS OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

6.6.1 Objective

The TraceMyFish project will also include a newsletter, making of videos, brochures etc. Intended for consumers, the industry, as well as the general public.

6.6.2 Description

Any communication and dissemination material that is not directly classified to the earlier mentioned activities are included in this section.

This contains the making of videos, brochures, one-pagers, etc. This material will be promoted through the TraceMyFish homepage and social media, as well as included in oral/poster presentations, as teaching material in university and training courses, webinars etc.

6.6.3 Status after year 1 (M12) and planned activities for year 2

More diverse means of communication and dissemination will be applied during year 2 of the project, in association with the production of more results.

7 SCHEDULED DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES AND HUMAN CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES PER PARTNER

This section includes the template in which the scheduled dissemination and communication activities, as well as intended human capacity building activities are provided from each partner. This schedule will be updated continuously and reported annually (D7.2- D7.5).

This template will be provided to each TraceMyFish participant through the Google Docs workspace.

Individual partner dissemination and communication schedule.

All updates on Dissemination and communication activities of the individual partners during project year 1 are marked in blue text.

7.1 SCiO

Partner Number: 1	Partner Acronym: SCiO	Person(s) in Charge: Panagiotis Zervas
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Actors across the fish value chain for whom data analysis and monitoring is valuable, namely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fishing boat owners/managers ○ Apothecary/inventory managers ○ Transportation companies ○ Retailers 	
Dissemination & Communication Activities	Conferences/Events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data Innovation Summit (https://datainnovationsummit.com/) ▪ AI & Big Data Expo (https://www.ai-expo.net/europe/) ▪ World Summit AI (https://worldsummit.ai/) ▪ European Big Data Value Forum 2023 (https://www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/) Status at M12 (October 2022) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Physical presence to AI and big data-related events is expected to be done during the 2nd year of the project when iFMS will be ready to be demonstrated 	
	Scientific Journals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A 	
	Public reach magazines <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Startupper (https://startupper.gr/) ▪ Ypaithros Chora (https://www.ypaithros.gr/) ▪ Agro24 (https://www.agro24.gr/) Status at M12 (October 2022) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interview of Dr. Panagiotis Zervas (Coordinator of the project) about the aim of the project at powergame.gr a Greek information portal: https://tinyurl.com/2p92cb6b 2. Interview of Dr. Pythagoras Karampiperis (CEO of SCiO) about the aim of the project to EPT3 Greek national TV channel 	
	Events Participation / Industry Events	

	<p>To be determined during the course of the project and as it produces demonstrable results</p> <p>Status at M12 (October 2022)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "AI for Industry and Business" online event organized by the Hellenic Federation of Enterprises on 23rd of March 2022 (https://tinyurl.com/mrmy5s3) 2. CivTech Alliance Global Scale-up Programme 2, Challenge 2: Green Public Procurement, Tech Online Day on 21st of October 2022
Individual Dissemination Plan	<p>SCiO's dissemination plan includes two main strands, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination via online means and specifically (a) social media channels, (b) press publications and news items via various publication channels (i.e., web-portals, newspapers etc) and (c) webinars for presenting the project results ▪ Dissemination via offline means, namely participation with booths to key events related to FoodTech, AI & Big Data analytics <p>Status at M12 (October 2022)</p> <p>The individual dissemination plan remains unchanged.</p>
Dissemination Means to be employed	<p>SCiO will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Share posts about the project via the company's social media channels such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn (which include more than 1,500 followers) ▪ Prepare news items about the project and share via web portals with broad outreach that focus on the FoodTech Startups ecosystem. <p>Participate in virtual and physical events as the ones mentioned in the relevant section (Dissemination & Communication), where the project's results can be presented and showcased to potential users and future adopters.</p>
Running or upcoming EU projects TraceMyFish could cooperate with	<p>At the moment, sibling BlueBio projects are those most fit to establish liaisons and future collaborations</p>
Human Capacity Building Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A

7.2 AUA

Partner Number: 2	Partner Acronym: AUA	Person(s) in Charge: George-John Nychas
Target Groups	Academia, industrial stakeholders within fishing value chain (specifically Mediterranean seabream/seabass value chain)	
Dissemination & Communication Activities	<p>Conferences/Events (at least two in the following)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EFFoST ▪ Wefta ▪ IAFP (Aberdeen, Europe) ▪ IAFP (USA) ▪ 	

	<p>Status at M12 (October 2022) AUA participated in RAFA conference (Proceedings of the 10th International Symposium on Recent Advances in Food Analysis (RAFA),6-9 September 2022, Prague, Czech Republic) with a poster presentation entitled “ Multispectral imaging (MSI) coupled with machine learning for the evaluation of authenticity in several seafood”</p> <p>Scientific Journals (at least two in the following)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food Control • LWT-Food Science and Technology • MDPI – Foods • MDPI – Applied Sciences • Food Research International • Scientific reports <p>Status at M12 (October 2022) MDPI publication – under preparation</p> <p>Public reach magazines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ N/A <p>Events Participation / Industry Events</p> <p>AUA envisions and plans to disseminate results within the context of food related scientific conferences on an international level e.g., EFFoST, WEFTA, and IAFP</p> <p>Status at M12 (October 2022) Apart from RAFA conference (mentioned above), AUA participated in Researcher's night (>15000 visitors) in Athens (September 2022) having the opportunity to present the concept of the TMF project as well as to demonstrate the VideometerLite</p>
<p>Individual Dissemination Plan</p>	<p>AUA’s dissemination involves the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination via online means and specifically <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) social media channels, (b) press publications and news items via various publication channels (i.e., web-portals, newspapers etc.) (c) webinars for presenting the project results (d) contributions to project newsletter, public news articles etc. (e) meetings and/or seminars with related stakeholders
<p>Dissemination Means to be employed</p>	<p>AUA will be employ news and posts on AUA’s homepage to communicate the project and the corresponding outcomes, magazines, scientific publications, oral/poster presentations in conferences and finally joint events with the participation of related stakeholders.</p>
<p>Running or upcoming EU projects TraceMyFish could cooperate with</p>	<p>Connection Ditect H2020 project (https://ditect.eu/).</p> <p>Other related BlueBio projects are under consideration</p>

Human Capacity Building Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-3 post doc fellowship (~2 years) • VideometerLite performance and training. • Student exchange. <p>Status at M12 (October 2022)</p> <p>Anastasia Lytou (member of the AUA team) visited VIDEOMETER premises in Copenhagen and joined VIDEOMETER team for a couple of weeks in April 2022. During this visit, she trained on VideometerLite and several other tools and software that will be used in the TMF project</p>
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7.3 NTNU

Partner Number: 3	Partner Acronym: NTNU	Person(s) in Charge: Jørgen Lerfall
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Academia and industrial stakeholders with the interest of improved traceability along the seafood value chain: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Food scientists ○ Atlantic salmon producers ○ Salmon slaughtering and processing owners ○ Retailers 	
Dissemination & Communication Activities	<p>Conferences/Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EFFoST (https://www.fffost.org/home/default.aspx) ▪ WEFTA (https://www.wefta.org/tp-32145-2/news/news#!section) ▪ AquaNor (https://aquanor.no/en/) <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>Due to delayed generation of data in the salmon pilot, it was not possible to attend any scientific conferences within the first year. However, we are aiming to present the project at next year's EFFoST and WEFTA conferences.</p>	
	<p>Scientific Journals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LWT-Food Science and Technology • Journal of Food Engineering • Food Research International • Scientific reports • Aquaculture <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>Due to delayed generation of data in the salmon pilot, it was not possible to write any scientific publications within the first year. However, we are aiming 1-2 papers to be written within the project's year two</p>	
	<p>Public reach magazines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Global aquaculture advocate (https://www.globalseafood.org/blog/tag/global-aquaculture-advocate/) ▪ Norsk Sjømat (https://sjomatbedriftene.no/norsk-sjomat/) <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>No articles not yet written, however, we are aiming to write a manuscript to be submitted to Norsk Sjømat, in spring 2023.</p>	

	<p>Events Participation / Industry Events</p> <p>NTNU plans to participate and present results on scientific conferences and events such as EFFoST, WEFTA, and AquaNor.</p> <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>The consortium participated at this year’s EFFoST conference but did not have any data from the project to present. However, next year we are aiming to present results at both EFFoST and WEFTA.</p>
<p>Individual Dissemination Plan</p>	<p>NTNU’s dissemination plan includes two main strands, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination via online means and specifically (a) social media channels, (b) press publications and news items via various publication channels (i.e., web-portals, newspapers etc) and (c) webinars for presenting the project results ▪ Dissemination via offline means, namely participation with booths to key events related to Food Science and Aquaculture
<p>Dissemination Means to be employed</p>	<p>NTNU will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Share posts about the project via social media channels such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn ▪ Publish scientific data from the project reaching both academia and relevant industrial stakeholders ▪ Participate in virtual and physical events as the ones mentioned in the relevant section (Dissemination & Cooperation), where the project’s results can be presented and showcased to potential users and future adopters.
<p>Running or upcoming EU projects TraceMyFish could cooperate with</p>	<p>At the moment, sibling BlueBio projects are those most fit to establish liaisons and future collaborations</p>
<p>Human Capacity Building Activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One post doc fellowship (2 years) • 1-2 MSc students annually • Short-medium time mobility for 2 persons times two <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>We are still searching for a post doctor candidate that fits the project, interviews have been conducted and hopefully the candidate is on board M1 2023. There is one MSc student working on the project at NTNU and two persons were on a short term mobility to UiO M3 2022.</p>

7.4 VIDEOM

Partner Number: 4	Partner VIDEOM	Acronym:	Person(s) in Charge: Nette Schultz
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Players within the seafood industry in all levels of the supply chain: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harvesting/fishing - Processing - Transporting - Retailers 		
Dissemination & Communication Activities	Conferences/Events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IASIM, Conference on spectral imaging in Esbjerg, Denmark, July 3rd-6th 2022. (T7.3 and T8.1) 		
	Scientific Journals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A 		
	Public reach magazines <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PlusProces, article in Danish magazine 		
	Events Participation / Industry Events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ANUGA Foodtec (T7.3 and T8.1) in Cologne, Germany April 26th - 29th, 2022 		
Individual Dissemination Plan	<p>Videometer’s dissemination plan includes two main strands, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination via online means and specifically (a) social media channels, (b) webinars for presenting Videometer technology (d) quarterly newsletter for Videometer stakeholders (more than 800 subscribers) ▪ Dissemination via offline means, namely participation with booths to key events related FoodTech, Spectral Imaging and Machine Vision 		
Dissemination Means to be employed	<p>Videometer will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Share posts about the project via the company’s social media channels such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn (which include more than 1,500 followers) ▪ Prepare news items about the project and share via web portals with broad outreach that focus on the FoodTech and Machine Vision industries. <p>Participate in virtual and physical events as the ones mentioned in the relevant section (Dissemination & Cooperation), where the project’s results can be presented and showcased to potential users and future adopters and prepare workshops.</p>		
Running or upcoming EU projects TraceMyFish could cooperate with	DiTECT		
Human Capacity Building Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars for training on Videometer technology • Young researcher exchange 		

7.5 UOI

Partner Number: 5	Partner Acronym: Uoi	Person(s) in Charge: María Guðjónsdóttir
Target Groups	Scientific community, fishing industry, consumers.	
Dissemination & Communication Activities	<p>Conferences/Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At least one annual conference/meeting participation planned. ▪ Potential conferences: WEFTA, EFFoST etc. <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>Conference participations have been delayed due to slower data generation within the whitefish value chain. However, the participation and presentation of TraceMyFish activities are planned for the WEFTA 2023 in Copenhagen, as well as other scientific conferences.</p>	
	<p>Scientific Journals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least one annual scientific peer reviewed publication planned. • Potential journals include Food Chemistry, Journal of Food Engineering, LWT Food Science and Technology, MDPI-Foods. <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>The activities within the PhD student Andrea Rakel Sigurðardóttir's research project include 5 publications, in which 4 are 3 are directly linked to the TraceMyFish research activities. Data gathering is currently ongoing, and these three publications are assumed to be submitted for publication within the year 2023.</p>	
	<p>Public reach magazines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At least one annual public news article, or other news media planned. ▪ Potential public reach magazines: TBD <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>Information on the TraceMyFish project has been promoted through the project's social media platforms, as well as through the Facebook page of the Faculty of Food Science and Nutrition at the University of Iceland. The Faculty Facebook page has a steady fanbase of 795 followers. This platform will be further utilized during the communication and dissemination of activities in the second project year. Publications in the marine news paper Ægir, and in other news media are also planned to take place in the second project year.</p>	
	<p>Events Participation / Industry Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stakeholder meetings with Lýsi and BRIM, March 2022. BRIM interested in testing of Videometer technologies in their value chains. ▪ Stakeholder meeting with ÚR, April 4th, 2022: Producer of frozen fish products interested in adding quality monitoring with the VideometerLite and VideometerLab instruments for the onboard freezing processes. Activities planned in unison with Icelandic domestically funded research project "Bætt nýting vinnsluferla við sjófrystingu karfa" - Matvælasjóður / Improved processes of onboard freezing of redfish" ▪ Further stakeholder meetings planned in Iceland. 	

	<p>Status at M12:</p> <p>In addition to the abovementioned stakeholder meetings UoI has participated in the following events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder meetings with BRIM in Iceland on September 21st and October 12th, 2022, for planning of whitefish value chain activities. • Stakeholder meetings with Vísir hf, followed up by e-mail correspondence in October 2022 on Anasakis detection trials within the whitefish value chain, and planning of PhD student Andrea Rakeł Sigurðardóttir doctoral project. • Discussions with QualiSea BlueBio Cofund consortium on potential synergies between the projects. TraceMyFish techniques are likely to be valuable for seaweed quality assessment during the spring harvest in 2023. • Discussions with Sustainable Healthy Diets consortium on potential synergies between projects. Non-destructive quality assessment fits well into strategies for increased sustainability within food production. Potential synergies identified for utilization of the TracMyFish techniques for product development from underutilized raw materials within the Sustainable Healthy diets project.
<p>Individual Dissemination Plan</p>	<p>UoI's dissemination plan include the following strands, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dissemination via online means and specifically <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) scientific article writing and publication, (b) conference participation, (c) the project homepage (design and updates) (d) social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook), (e) contributions to project newsletter, public news articles etc. (f) stakeholder meetings and seminars <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>The overall individual dissemination plan of UoI is unchanged from the original plan, although some delays have been seen due to delays in other WPs. Among achieved activities in year 1 are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launching of TraceMyFish homepage • Launching of TraceMyFish social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook) • Participation in Videometer training seminars • Stakeholder engagement participation <p>Added focus will be put into achieving the remaining dissemination and communication objectives.</p>
<p>Dissemination Means to be employed</p>	<p>UoI will be use the following dissemination means News and posts on homepage, social media, magazines, scientific publications, oral/poster presentations, and stakeholder event participation</p> <p>Status at M12: Unchanged from original plan.</p>
<p>Running or upcoming EU projects TraceMyFish could cooperate with</p>	<p>QualiSea - show interest in using the VideometerLite and VideometerLab techniques for seaweed quality monitoring</p> <p>Biozoostain – potential utilization of the VideometerLab techniques for process monitoring and product development.</p>

	<p>Sustainable Healthy Diets - potential utilization of the Videometer techniques for process monitoring and product development.</p> <p>AccelWater – potential utilization of the Videometer techniques for process monitoring and product development.</p>
<p>Human Capacity Building Activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videometer setup and training in Iceland finished in March 2022. Feedback meeting with Videometer on May 4th on VideometerLite performance. • Stakeholder meetings and seminars. • Student exchange. <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>In addition to the above mentioned activities the following HCB activities have taken place:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in stakeholder meetings and gatherings as listed in the report • Launching of PhD project of Andrea Rakeł Sigurðardóttir, who is supervised by partners from UoI, Matís and Videometer. • Planned PhD student exchange activities between NTNU and UoI/Matís in January 2023.

7.6 MATIS

Partner Number: 6	Partner Acronym: Matís	Person(s) in Charge: Hildur Inga Sveinsdóttir
Target Groups	Scientific community, fishing industry, consumers.	
Dissemination & Communication Activities	<p>Conferences/Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At least one annual conference/meeting participation planned. ▪ Potential conferences: WEFTA, EFFoST etc. <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>Conference participations have been delayed due to slower data generation within the whitefish value chain. However, the participation and presentation of TraceMyFish activities are planned for the WEFTA 2023 in Copenhagen, as well as other scientific conferences.</p> <p>BlueBio Cofund meeting, October 6th, 2022. TraceMyFish presentation by Matís.</p>	
	<p>Scientific Journals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least one annual scientific peer reviewed publication planned. • Potential journals include Food Chemistry, Journal of Food Engineering, LWT Food Science and Technology, MDPI-Foods. <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>The activities within the PhD student Andrea Raket Sigurðardóttir's research project include 5 publications, in which 4 are 3 are directly linked to the TraceMyFish research activities. Matís is co-supervising the PhD student, and provides research facilities for her work. Data gathering is currently ongoing, and these three publications are assumed to be submitted for publication within the year 2023.</p>	
	<p>Public reach magazines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At least one annual public news article, or other news media planned. ▪ Potential public reach magazines: TBD 	
	<p>Events Participation / Industry Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stakeholder meetings with Lýsi and BRIM, March 2022. BRIM interested in testing of Videometer technologies in their value chains. ▪ Stakeholder meeting with ÚR, April 4th 2022: Producer of frozen fish products interested in adding quality monitoring with the VideometerLite and VideometerLab instruments for the onboard freezing processes. Activities planned in unison with Icelandic domestically funded research project "Bætt nýting vinnsluferla við sjófrýstingu karfa" - Matvælasjóður / Improved processes of onboard freezing of redfish". ▪ Further stakeholder meetings planned in Iceland. <p>Status at M12:</p> <p>In addition to the abovementioned stakeholder meetings UoI has participated in the following events:</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder meetings with BRIM in Iceland on September 21st and October 12th, 2022, for planning of whitefish value chain activities. Stakeholder meetings with Vísir hf, followed up by e-mail correspondence in October 2022 on Anasakis detection trials within the whitefish value chain, and planning of PhD student Andrea Rakeł Sigurðardóttir doctoral project. Discussions with QualiSea BlueBio Cofund consortium on potential synergies between the projects. TraceMyFish techniques are likely to be valuable for seaweed quality assessment during the spring harvest in 2023. <p>Discussions with Sustainable Healthy Diets consortium on potential synergies between projects. Non-destructive quality assessment fits well into strategies for increased sustainability within food production. Potential synergies identified for utilization of the TracMyFish techniques for product development from underutilized raw materials within the Sustainable Healthy diets project.</p>
<p>Individual Dissemination Plan</p>	<p>Matís’s dissemination plan include the following strands, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination via online means and specifically <ol style="list-style-type: none"> scientific article writing and publication, conference participation, contributions to the project homepage contributions to social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook), contributions to project newsletter, public news articles etc. stakeholder meetings and seminars <p>Status at M12: Unchanged from original plan.</p>
<p>Dissemination Means to be employed</p>	<p>UoI will be use the following dissemination means News and posts on homepage, social media, magazines, scientific publications, oral/poster presentations, and stakeholder event participation</p>
<p>Running or upcoming EU projects TraceMyFish could cooperate with</p>	<p>QualiSea - show interest in using the VideometerLite and VideometerLab techniques for seaweed quality monitoring Biozoostain – potential utilization of the VideometerLab techniques for process monitoring and product development. AccelWater – potential utilization of the Videometer techniques for process monitoring and product development.</p>
<p>Human Capacity Building Activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Videometer setup and training in Iceland finished in March 2022. Feedback meeting with Videometer on May 4th on VideometerLite performance. Stakeholder meetings and seminars. Student exchange. <p>Status at M12: In addition to the above mentioned activities the following HCB activities have taken place:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in stakeholder meetings and gatherings as listed in the report

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Launching of PhD project of Andrea Rakeł Sigurđardóttir, who is supervised by partners from UoI, Matís and Videometer. <p>Planned PhD student exchange activities between NTNU and UoI/Matís in January 2023.</p>
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8 CONCLUSIONS

The communications and dissemination plan will be revised and updated and reported on continuously throughout the project duration in D7.2-7.5. The key performance indicators identified for each activity provide easy monitoring of the effectiveness of the different means of communication and eases the assessment of whether all intended goals of the TraceMyFish project have been reached at the end of the project duration.

After the first year of the TraceMyFish projects most KPI parameters set for the first 12 months are close to or already fulfilled. More detailed data acquisitions in the first months of 2023 will provide input for further publications, presentation at scientific and industrial events, and for the preparation of diverse communications and dissemination materials. The KPIs for year 2 are thus all likely to be achieved within the project duration.